

CO-OPERAS workshop

FAIR data and Social Sciences and Humanities

Torino September 10, 2019

Programme

- 10.00-10.30 Who are we? Informal presentations
- 10.30-11.00 Introduction: OPERAS, Co-OPERAS, FAIR principles (Elena Giglia, UniTO)
- 11.00-13.00 Focus Group (plenary): define “data” in the SSH
- 14.00-14.45 Individual exercise: how FAIR are the data I produce/use? [paper form]
- 14.45-15.45 Sharing results of the individual exercise

Organizers

Elena Giglia (Univ. Turin/CO-OPERAS)
Arnaud Gingold (OpenEdition/CO-OPERAS)

Participants

19 researchers; disciplinary areas:

Archaeology
Classical studies (latin literature)
Cultural Heritage
Digital Humanities
Economy
French literature
Hindology
History
History of Philosophy
International Law
Library sciences
Linguistics
Philology
Philosophy
Sociology

SOME ISSUES THEY AGREED ON (IN GENERAL)

- **metadata are crucial, and they can not be separated from data**
- **lack of interoperability**, as methods and tools are linked to specific projects
- **we need to preserve the specificity of the tradition of the Humanities**
- there is a need of **guidelines on metadata**, and a **minimum set of metadata** to integrate/expand in order to share at least a common layer
- more training needed on **Digital Humanities and data/metadata skills**
- more training on **information engineering**, need of a wider range of skills
- a setback: communities are **conservatives**
- **communities of practice are urgently needed** in order to **build a common basic metadata standard** + all the relatives **extensions** + all the tools

- **virtual research environments** to be created to **facilitate the adoption of standards**
- the exercise on the level of FAIRness was really appreciated as it made them ask themselves **questions never asked before** on the data they use on a daily basis
- creating **ontologies is a philosophical matter**, not a computer science issue

First session

FOCUS GROUP ON DATA IN THE SSH

Lively discussion - recalling Saint Augustin and the definition of time: you know what it is unless you are asked about -, following the suggestion not to reduce “data” to the information science conceptual framework.

Some of the proposed definitions:

- **data as a process**: data are dynamic and diachronic, they have to represent and preserve a process. That’s why metadata are crucial and they can’t be separated from the data.
- **data as words**, they provide the basis of the knowledge. Distinguish between data and abstraction, on which you can build specialistic analysis. By “process” we should consider a) access to data b) participation in the creation of knowledge
- **data are anything you can formalize through a language**, should “language” be any ontology, mark-up, method that formalize (e.g. TEI encoding schema). Data and metadata are indivisible
- **“data” is misleading**, as nowadays we have devices able to record as “data” anything which used to be unobserved/unimportant. Let’s talk instead of
 - **weak documents**, mere factual recordings
 - **strong documents**, whenever a deliberate act generates it
- **data are “documents” only when and if we have a method to collect/obtain**
- **data are expression of a method**: if the method was tailored for a specific project/research question, interoperability is at stake
- **“paradata” as “upon what method have the data been generated”** is an important conceptual step
- **data are functional to information**: it’s something I can provide my interpretation on
- **“record”** is a more suitable term than data
- **data** can only exist if anyone has **created them**: e.g. in archaeology the mere recording seems objective, as you start describing it, subjectivity is immediately involved
- we have **a few “data” as interpretation and subjectivity** come early into play
- we have **a few “raw data”** as to be analyzed they have to be treated somehow
- **data are usually discussed** in the SSH, while in the hard sciences they often come from a machine, so there is no debate
- **data and their quality** depend also on your research perspective: you need a perfect reproduction of a manuscript if you need to locate it by the depth/characteristics of the line, whereas if you are only interested in the content any reproduction will do
- **books and articles** are research outputs but at the same time they can be **“data” for new researches**

- in history knowledge is created through a cycle non affected by the digital world; most of the evidence is still analogic. Metadata are crucial to discover it
- in **economy** you can find **standardized data in primary sources** as official financial statements, but whenever you introduce a choice of variables and sources you have to clearly describe your method and choices. If not, data are not reusable

Second session

WHAT WE THINK OF “FAIR”

- **are we, the researchers, who use these resources without asking how data were created or described, part of the problem?**
- it's mostly a matter of **cultural change**, as technically we have been using FAIR tools (as TEI) for ages
- **copyright is a barrier to R-Reuse**
- F-A-I are functional to **R-Reuse which is the final goal**
- R-Reuse, is crucial but we also need to **train our students** to share their resources and data
- making **analogic data FAIR is a priority**, as they constitute the basis for any further interpretation/analysis. **Metadata enrichment is thus crucial**
- in order to be **R, reusable**, you also need to have **Reliable** data
- underline that **“Accessible” does not mean Open**
- we already use some persistent identifiers as DOIs or ORCID, go on finding some structured part of a paper in order to extract meaningful information

GENERAL ISSUES AFTER THE EXERCISE ON FAIRNESS

- **data and metadata skills** should be included in curricula at an early stage
- need of **standardization of methods** so they can be univocally recalled

FINDABLE

- lack of **thesauri or authority files** to enable content search
- lack of **indexes**
- lack of **unique identifiers or standards**
- lack of **quality in metadata**
- **obsolescence of the URLs**

ACCESSIBLE

- **lack of a single database**, data are fragmented in several sources
- texts **digitized as images, not searchable**
- texts **digitized without diacritical**
- need of **specific software to read**
- **phonetic transcript** not always reliable

INTEROPERABLE

- **lack of controlled vocabulary**
- **issues in format conversion**
- **need of ontologies, vocabularies and specialized authority files**
- **need of convergence on a single transcription system**

- **corpora have many layers**, so interoperability is even more complex

REUSABLE

- **copyright** is the main issues, as regulation varies in any country
- **lack of licences associated to databases**
- **lack of skills to associate the appropriate licence**
- need of **legal advice** on use and reuse and to answer to questions like “who is the right owner in supercorpora”?
- lack of **provenance** details (and scarcely standardized when present)
- without documentation on method/choices it’s impossible to reuse
- reuse of books: copyright issues, the rights holder is not easy to detect
- contracts with non-Open Access publishers don’t allow reuse
- Reuse should be associated to **READABLE (INTELLEGIBLE), RELEVANCE, RELIABLE, RESILIENCE**
- Reuse should be a measure to validate a resource